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DEVELOPMENT AND VALIDATION OF AN ENGLISH LANGUAGE LEARNING MODULE

FRINCESS T. FLORES, LPT

Master of Arts in Education Major in English Student

Tarlac State University

Region III (Central Luzon)

Chapter 1

THE PROBLEM AND ITS BACKGROUND

Background of the study

Communicating effectively and efficiently in English has grown more and more crucial in today's globalized world. English is the universal language in many fields, including academia, business, and technology. As a result, individuals worldwide seek to acquire English language skills to enhance their educational and career prospects.

Other countries are perceived to be successful in the enhancement of English. However, the odds of the effectiveness of the teaching, as well as the learning process of the language in the last three years are evidently on the Philippines' side. The country trails other nations worldwide for the standard of education, particularly when it comes to learning the English language. The Philippines' English Proficiency Index (EPI) score declined from 592 in 2020 to 578 in 2022, ranking 22nd among the 111 economies whose population does not have English as a first language, as presented in the EF EPI 2022 report (EF EPI 2022 – EF English Proficiency Index – Philippines, n.d.). This implies that, even with the implementation of the language as a medium of education and the use of standardized materials in elementary, secondary, and even private schools and universities, there may be no assurance of efficiency. Despite being the world's third-largest English-speaking country, with over 95% of the population knowing English and having access to online resources, the quality of English language education is still a concern.

Moreover, we can say that having nothing could lead to numerous problems. Problems like the one encountered by a Filipino passenger struggling to pass her fare due to her inability to use the English language in a basic interaction with a foreigner. How come a simple interaction with a foreigner seems hard for most people in the country? How is a simple "Excuse me, would you mind passing my fare (amount) to the driver?" hard for most of us?

The foregoing difficulty could be attributed to a variety of variables influencing Filipinos' choice of materials for learning and practicing their target language. Inadequate materials for the instruction and learning process, misalignment of resources with the educational context, and an improper format for the learners' age and needs constitute a few of the issues that impede learning effectiveness.

In addition to the factors that hinder learning, the nature of the materials can also be pointed out as one of the culprits when it comes to not acquiring the best language learning and

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use. The fact that the materials are bought by teachers and not made specifically for their subject says it all. Standardized learning materials may only cater to some children's individual needs and learning styles. Each child learns differently, and a rigid, standardized approach may hinder their ability to grasp concepts effectively. A study by Popham (2020) found that standardized materials failed to cater to individual differences, leading to lower student motivation and engagement levels. The issue is that what is included in the original materials is the basis for the teacher in teaching the subject unless the teacher has many references. However, using more than one source for a lesson could lead to a lot of information and theories that do not match up, which could tire out both the teacher and the students.

Moreover, the scarcity of published English materials must be considered an issue escalating the inefficacy of learning and using the language. A study by Johnson and Garcia (2022) revealed that students in schools with limited access to published learning materials had lower scores on standardized tests than those with adequate access.

In addition, teachers need more reference materials. Teachers need more learning materials to help and enhance student learning.

Equally important is that due to the scarcity of materials at school, the materials may tend to cover broader concepts about a topic; thus, it becomes harder for learners to digest all the information needed for the lesson. That being said, issues of importance regarding which lessons must be included and taught may arise.

Various methods and resources have been developed to facilitate English language learning in response to this growing demand. Effective materials should be designed to meet learners' needs by providing relevant content that is organized in a logical sequence with clear instructions and feedback. One such resource is the English language learning module, which is a structured instructional tool designed to assist students learn and improve their proficiency in English.

During the COVID-19 outbreak, a university in Region III which is accredited as Center for Teacher Education began developing modules. The university president's office issued a memorandum in April 2020 concerning the development of teaching modules as part of the flexible learning plan of action for the academic year immediately following an enhanced community quarantine. The purpose of the plan was to cope with the situation and to start the new normal of instruction. Due to the new normal of instruction, faculty members were tasked to prepare and develop modules for their subjects.

For the said university, developing modules is just the initial step in achieving the goal in a new normal of instruction. On June 2020, another memo following the development of modules was passed across all colleges. The memorandum order no. 17, series 2020, served as the follow up memo requiring an intensive process which are the specifications on the minimum requirement for the prescribed format of the to be developed modules and the suggested guidelines in the evaluation of the developed modules.

Following the directions, the researcher of this study, who happens to be a faculty member at the university, was able to develop several modules, one of which was for the subject EL 118 - Language Learning Materials Development (LLMD). The module was developed in accordance with the Memorandum Order No. 75, Series of 2017 of the Commission on Higher Education (CHED), for the Bachelor of Secondary Education (BSED) English curriculum. EL 118 or ELT – Language Learning Materials Development is one out of the 21 major courses listed in the said memorandum.

Like any other developed modules, English language learning modules have gained popularity due to their potential to provide structured and comprehensive learning experiences. These modules often contain a variety of language skills such as reading, writing, listening, and speaking, and they typically include interactive exercises and multimedia components. However,

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despite their widespread use, there needs to be standardized and validated English language learning modules that cater to learners' diverse needs and proficiency levels.

Although LLMD related materials can be downloaded online, the need for a module that will serve as the primary reference for a particular subject is integral. This may be perceived as the answer to one of classroom's challenges which is the lack of materials in delivering quality instruction. As emphasized in the study of Gueta and Janer (2021), educational quality must be addressed in various ways, including ensuring that appropriate materials for instruction and learning are available for a program. As Smith et al. (2023) emphasized, students in resource-constrained schools demonstrated lower levels of enthusiasm for learning than students with access to various learning materials. All the reasons mentioned drive the researcher to push through with the research.

This study sought to fill these gaps by redeveloping an English language learning module to make it more accessible, adaptive, and effective for learners in a wide variety of contexts. Other significant reasons for the redevelopment of the material are to show originality by simplifying language use and providing meaningful activities in the module catering to the users' linguistic abilities and needs, to shift from the usual content-based to a task-based approach, and to be able to come up with a cost-efficient material that, at the same time, can be utilized in various set-ups, including face-to-face learning and online environment. These are intended to provide more effective instruction in explaining and providing specific materials for the areas of English and to enhance learning through the module despite limited resources at the university. It is hoped that this innovation will respond to the urgent need for materials for higher education. More importantly, the researcher knew that the developed material can only be helpful if tested for validity.

Statement of the Objectives

The research aimed to develop and validate an English Language Learning Module for third-year English Major students.

Specifically, the researcher sought to accomplish all of the following objectives:

1. Develop an English Language Learning Module for the 3rd Year English Major students.
2. Determine the level of acceptability of the module through expert validation concerning the following:
 - 2.1. objectives
 - 2.2. contents
 - 2.3. format
 - 2.4. language use
 - 2.5. presentation
 - 2.6. usefulness
3. Ascertain the effectiveness of the module based on the following:
 - 3.1. scores in the pretest of the control and experimental groups;
 - 3.2. scores in the post-test of the control and experimental groups;
 - 3.3. scores in the pretest and post-test of the control group;
 - 3.4. scores in the pretest and post-test of the experimental group;
4. Check for significant differences in participant efficacy as revealed by the pretest and post-test.
5. Draw implications from the study for the teaching and learning of English.

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Hypotheses

1. The pretest scores of the control and experimental groups were not significantly different.
2. The post-test scores of the control and experimental groups were not significantly different.
3. The control group's pretest and posttest scores were not significantly different.
4. The experimental group's pretest and posttest scores were not significantly different.

Significance of the Study

This study was carried out to develop and validate an English language learning module for the subject Language Learning Materials Development. This study also benefited the following:

To the **College of Teacher Education**. The output of the study was served as an effective material to facilitate both distance and face-to-face learning. The developed and validated material may also be used as a reference for Language Learning Materials Development teachers of the College of Teacher Education and other colleges and universities offering the course. Also, the material would be added to the books and other resources in the school library.

To the **English teachers of the College of Teacher Education**. The developed and validated material consisted of varied supporting materials, activities, links, and tests that would be of great help to teachers teaching the areas of English. Knowing what material, activity, and test to use for a specific area in English, which would be seen in the output of this study, would provide teachers with new ideas on how to deliver their classes more effectively than in the traditional and typical approach. This study was served as a basis for them to improve their teaching methods, promoting "enjoying while learning" to students.

To the **students of the College of Teacher Education**. As future teachers, the exposure and practice of the materials, activities, links, and tests found in the output of this study was served as their basis for making their classroom and teaching enjoyable and fruitful. The exposure to the mentioned in the output would equip them for a better way of teaching. By doing the things listed in the output, they could find suitable materials, activities, and tests for a particular area of English.

To the **materials developer**. The appearance and structure of the output of this study would serve as a point of reference for the developers in creating their material. The results of this study could also be changed in any way if the developers of the material decided in the future that the material needed to be changed.

To the **future researchers**. This would serve as a starting point for further research relevant to the topic of study.

Scope and Delimitation

This study sought to develop and validate an English Language Learning Module—particularly for course Language Learning Materials Development. This addressed the concerns of teachers and students over the lack of adequate materials to provide more effective instruction in explaining, and giving specialized materials for the areas of English, as well as to boost learning through the module, despite limited resources at the university.

The developed and validated material is a module for third-year College of Teacher Education students majoring in English, and also for the college's English teachers assigned to teach the subject.

The content and structure of the material corresponded to the teaching-learning outcomes of the Language Learning Materials Development course offered by the College of Teacher Education at Tarlac State University.

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Five experts in the English language—preferably professors from state universities—served as the validators of the module. The module was validated by experts using the five-point Likert criteria borrowed from Torre Franca's (2017) thesis. The criteria were determined based on the adopted instrument, encompassing format, objectives, language use, contents, presentation, and usefulness.

The study participants were mainly third-year English major students from the College of Education. The participants were selected based on the researcher's predetermined criteria, which considered factors like subject schedule, academic standing, year level, and major.

The Research and Development design served as the framework for conducting the study, with the goal of aiding in the development and validation of an instructional tool. The R&D design process consisted of three phases: preliminary, development, and evaluation.

Literature Review

English Language Learning Module

English Language Learning Modules (ELLMs) are educational resources created to assist learners in acquiring a particular English language proficiency. It can address a wide range of topics, from basic grammar principles to advanced reading comprehension. These self-contained units can be seamlessly incorporated into different learning settings, offering instructors and self-directed learners a systematic method for developing skills.

ELLMs can be used in the classroom to complement traditional textbooks or as the main instructional resource for specific subjects. Online learning platforms can utilize ELLMs to provide asynchronous instruction, accommodating learners with diverse schedules. Self-directed learners can take advantage of the targeted approach of ELLMs, addressing specific weaknesses to enhance their skills independently.

A typical ELLM follows a logical sequence in its structure. Learning objectives succinctly define the knowledge or skills that will be gained after finishing the module. The main content is presented clearly and accessibly, often using various instructional materials like text, audio, video, or interactive elements. Activities and exercises are integrated throughout the module to guarantee understanding and practical application. Assessments, like quizzes, self-reflection exercises, or writing assignments, help learners measure their comprehension and pinpoint areas that need more study.

The significance of a high-quality English language learning module is extremely noteworthy. Personalized and captivating materials enhance the learning process, aid in following a structured curriculum, increase student involvement, and enable immediate feedback and communication. Language educators create a supportive and effective learning environment by using well-designed educational materials, allowing students to achieve fluency and proficiency in English.

ELLMs accommodate various learning styles and paces, allowing instructors to adjust them according to their student's needs. Customized educational resources can be created to tackle the linguistic obstacles and cultural subtleties encountered by students in a specific area or group, resulting in a more individualized learning journey. Razak and Ismail (2017) emphasize that customized materials can cater to learners' varied abilities and learning styles, enhancing a personalized learning experience. Personalization can result in increased student engagement and improved knowledge retention.

Furthermore, a comprehensive English language learning module assists teachers in organizing their curriculum efficiently. An effectively structured syllabus, complemented by suitable learning materials, guarantees a comprehensive coverage of all language learning components including grammar, vocabulary, speaking, listening, reading, and writing in a

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methodical manner. The module's focused approach enhances comprehension and memory retention of particular English language skills. Additionally, meticulously crafted educational resources can enhance the learning process by delivering information in a coherent and structured format (Leffa & Gaies, 2018). It can improve language proficiency and communication skills.

Engaging learning materials are essential for capturing and sustaining students' interest in lessons. Utilizing interactive textbooks, audio-visual aids, role-playing exercises, and group activities can enhance the learning experience by making it dynamic and stimulating. A study conducted by Hafiz and Al-Mudimigh in 2015 found that using instructional materials correctly has a positive effect on students' attitudes towards learning, enhancing the effectiveness and enjoyment of the learning process. Students who perceive the materials as interesting and pertinent are more likely to remain motivated and concentrated on their studies.

Moreover, top-notch educational resources consist of exercises and evaluations that allow teachers to offer immediate feedback to students. Teachers can assess individual progress accurately and provide timely support to struggling students due to this prompt feedback.

Additionally, English language learning material provides students ample opportunities to practice and communicate in English with their peers and instructors. Engaging in conversations, debates, and presentations fosters language fluency and builds students' confidence in expressing themselves effectively.

Moreover, quality English language learning material lays the groundwork for students to progress to more advanced levels of language proficiency. By focusing on essential grammar rules, vocabulary building, and language usage, learners develop a solid foundation to serve them well as they continue their language journey.

Module

The need for better materials in the learning process is critical, but providing appropriate materials for learners is difficult, especially when a pandemic strikes the world and education systems appear to need help with where to gather materials. As the crisis worsens in 2020, educational institutions will turn to developing materials for students.

Developed materials are one of the tools that can assist teachers in conveying knowledge naturally, resulting in good teaching and learning processes (Koko, 2016). Primary and secondary tools and outlines used in teaching and learning can be classified as developed instructional materials. As a result, it is up to the teachers to determine the quality and appropriateness of the developed instructional materials. On one hand, instructional materials can help students learn more about the topics they are studying by directing them to additional resources. As revealed in the study of Chen et al. (2019), consistent use of well-structured and engaging instructional materials improved students' reading comprehension abilities. The study underlined the importance of providing continuous access to appropriate resources to sustain academic progress.

In the case of the institutions in the Philippines, the module is one of the appropriate materials. In addition to the many kinds of materials that a teacher may use to deliver lessons to a class, the module is widely used by schools—both private and public—for elementary learners and up. The module is a collection of learning opportunities structured methodically within a clearly defined topic that includes instructional components (Calderon et al., 1998). The module has become an increasingly common teaching approach in the school system (Nardo, 2017).

In the context of flexible learning, the development of modules is a way to mitigate the current set-up caused by the unexpected and massive transitions in education delivery during the pandemic. According to a study by Tarrayo and Anudin (2021), developing materials for flexible learning can help students learn more, create a classroom where everyone feels welcome, improve teachers' insights and methods, and give teachers more motivation and independence.

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The utilization of suitable instructional materials during the pedagogical process is a fundamental strategy for enhancing students' academic performance. Arguably, teaching without tools makes achieving teaching and learning goals and competency impossible. More learning materials can also strain teachers, who may need more resources to provide comprehensive instruction. Teachers may employ conventional lecture-based approaches, which may only address the learning requirements of certain students. According to a case study conducted by Brown et al. (2022), educators in educational institutions with restricted access to learning resources encountered difficulties in the implementation of efficacious pedagogical approaches and personalized instruction.

The utilization of instructional tools facilitates students in acquiring a more comprehensive comprehension of the subject matter through self-directed learning (IPROJECT Content Management Team, (2020). A study conducted by Adalikwu and Iorokpigh (2013) demonstrated that students who received instruction through instructional materials exhibited superior academic performance compared to those who did not. Utilizing instructional materials improved students' comprehension of the topics and led to increased academic performance. In classroom settings that are both engaging and purposeful, instructional materials are designed to stimulate, ignite, and facilitate desired transformations in students' learning capabilities, attitudes, and behaviors.

According to Campbell (1999), instructional materials play a crucial role in enhancing the teaching and learning process by providing valuable knowledge and skill-building information. Furthermore, they have been recognized as a potent approach for attaining efficient instruction and acquisition of knowledge. The practical deployment of high-quality and adequate instructional resources in the classroom serves as a demonstration of their significance in the process of learning and instruction. Indeed, instructional materials encompass a comprehensive range of resources that educators can utilize to enhance the level of engagement and memorability in the learning process (Tety, 2016). Because they contain tangible content that even learners can comprehend and relate to, instructional materials provide a variety of methods and strategies that facilitate the teaching and learning processes. Most educators seek systematic approaches to understanding disparities, particularly among students, throughout the teaching process due to the numerous benefits they provide.

The Use of Module

A module, a type of personalized teaching, enables learners to take advantage of a self-sufficient collection of learning exercises. Learners are led through these activities to acquire knowledge or the ability to perform a specific task. A learning module could also include exercises that assist learners in understanding specific concepts.

A module allows the learner greater autonomy over his or her education. It is a collection of educational possibilities organized around a well-defined theme. It consists of instructions, specific goals, instructional activities, and assessments using criterion-referenced measurement.

The module is a breakthrough that has occurred in both developed and developing countries, with its influence being driven by initiatives on module preparation and use carried out by numerous institutions, including the Department of Education. It is an educational resource exhibiting characteristics that will make the user an independent learner, allowing him to self-pace and improve at his speed while finally presenting him with a sense of self-satisfaction, which is the essence of modular education.

Language Learning Materials Development

Under the CHED Memo no. 75 of 2017, Language Learning Materials Development (LLMD) is one out of the 63 major courses that Higher Education Institutions (HEI) must offer to third year students majoring in English. The memorandum stipulates the rules, standards and procedures for

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Bachelor of Secondary Education (BSEd). According to Article II Section 2 of the order, State Universities and Colleges (SUCs) and Local Universities and Colleges (LUCs) must follow the policies and standards outlined in these documents.

In Tarlac State University – a known Center of Development university in Central Luzon - Language Learning Materials Development with code EL 118 is a course offered in the College of Education as part of the Bachelor of Secondary Education, Major in English curriculum. The code EL 118 is only true to the aforementioned university, for other universities have their own codes to use for their offered courses.

This LLMD course credits three (3) units and has a contact hour requirement of three (3) hours per week. This course is designed for the 3rd year major in English at any institution offering the same course code and major. Prerequisites for this course include Principles and Theories of Language Learning and Acquisition, as well as Mythology and Folklore. This course allows pre-service English teachers to choose, develop, produce, and evaluate diverse language teaching and learning tools based on defined K-12 competencies for learning. Participating in these activities allows them to exhibit subject mastery of the basics and techniques for developing language resources. The students demonstrate proficiency in using innovative ways to develop contextualized and localized teaching materials. These materials give chances to use language meaningfully, making it easier to learn and teach languages.

They are written in the same OBTL as LLMD, which consists of four (4) main packets or chapter lessons throughout the semester. Each packet contains key subtopics. The first chapter serves as an introduction to material development. The sub-topics are: (1) Definition of Materials and Materials Development, (2) Current Positive and Negative Trends and Issues in Materials Development, (3) Who Should Develop the Materials, (4) Principles of Second Language Acquisition (SLA) Relevant to Materials and Principles, and (5) Materials Development Procedures.

The second chapter discusses how to evaluate materials. As the topic title implies, students will apply principles and techniques to assess resources. This chapter's subtopics are (1) the Definition and Principles of Materials Evaluation, (2) Characteristics that every component of material should consider, and (3) Materials Evaluation Types.

The third chapter for this course is Adapting Materials. In this part of the lesson, the students will try to select materials to adapt. As part of the process of adaptation, modifications are expected from the students' adapted materials after their thorough reviews. (1) A teacher-and student-centered approach to materials adaptation; (2) the Primary Features of Materials Adaptation; and (3) Materials and Technology for Education.

The last packet of the course is about developing specific types of materials. Since the course is intended for students majoring in English, the focus of this chapter is the skills and competencies in the areas of English. The Materials for the Teaching of Grammar are sub-topic one (1). To deviate from the limitation of this part, the teacher may add other tasks like selection and collection of materials, besides discussing the criteria that should be met when adapting materials for grammar. Sub-topic two (2) is Materials for Teaching Vocabulary. This section focuses on devising input and output tasks to help students gain fluency and expand their vocabulary. Adding tasks for this part is also encouraged. Sub-topic three (3) is Materials for Developing Reading Skills. This part deals with the alternative approach to materials for teaching reading. Again, the teacher is allowed to do other tasks for this part. Developing materials for writing skills is sub-topic four (4). This sub-topic discusses the role of writing materials in the learning process. Selection and collection are also part of the task under this topic. Developing materials for speaking skills is sub-topic five (5). This part deals with the relevant materials for speaking. Selection and collection are ideal tasks for this part. Showcasing the trends in materials for this skill is also encouraged. Developing materials for listening skills is sub-topic six (6). This topic deals with the rich activities applicable to the skill of listening. Materials for Developing Viewing Skills is sub-topic 7. This talks about the materials that may enrich the skill. Lastly, sub-topic 8 is Materials for Cultural

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Awareness. This topic addresses both the cultural context of language and the linguistic component of culture. LLMD is composed of 4 main chapters, which are perceived as steps in the effective selection, collection, adaptation, modification, and development of materials for the different skills for the areas of English.

The materials and references used to teach this subject were taken online. The list of these materials and references are the following: (1) Developing Materials for Language Teaching by Brian Tomlinson. This has 21 Chapters with 3-6 sub-topics with a total of 35 pages. This is authored by Zahra Farajnezhad., (2) Introduction: principles and procedures of materials development of Tomlinson. This is the introduction part of the LLMD course, with a few snippets of material evaluation principles., (3) Principles and Procedures of Materials Development for Language Learning (Part 2) of Tomlinson. This article is a modified version of a section that was originally published in Tomlinson, B. (2010) Materials development principles and procedures., (4) Principles and Procedures of Materials Development for Language Learning by Brian Tomlinson authored by Veronica Ormeño. The uploaded material shows the six (6) principles of SLA relevant to materials development., and (5) Developing Learning Materials for Specific Purposes. The material provides information about materials development, principles, procedures, and a 2-page discussion for the topic "developing learning materials for specific purposes." This material authored by Y. M. Harsano has 11 total number of pages.

Farajnezhad (2022) emphasized in her description of the uploaded material on ResearchGate that the information provided is a RECAP of Brian Tomlinson's book Developing Materials for Language Teaching.

Tomlinson (2020) are extracted and adapted information from previous materials created by Tomlinson and other contributors mentioned in his books. 2 showcases a brief portion of the introduction part of the whole lesson for LLMD. 3, however, is a modified version of Tomlinson's Principles and procedures of materials development.

Ormeño (2022) uploaded a paper that adapts part of (Tomlinson, B., 2010) Principles and Procedures of Materials Development. The paper presents information regarding the principles of SLA relevant to materials development.

Harsano's (2015) paper discusses the development of teaching/learning materials for English for Specific Purposes (ESP). The definition, the rules, the process, and the actual work of making learning materials for ESP are all included in the description.

The Need for Language Learning Materials Development Module

A material that considers its users must be developed to mediate between the course content, the teachers, and the pupils (Tomlinson, 2016 & Bouckaert, 2018). Some things to consider are the users' needs, learning styles, strengths, capacity to learn, capability to use the material, address weaknesses, and disparity in financial and emotional well-being.

As provided earlier, LLMD materials providing concepts, opinions, evidence, and theories are available online. Although the materials are accessible online, the challenges of reading, browsing, skimming, and scanning the materials without having them printed will become a burden and not a help for them to learn. In order to mitigate the issue, developing materials that are easy to access, relatable, contextualized, straightforward, and cheap but with the same quality – a module – is a must. Studies have shown the impact of using developed instructional materials on students' academic achievement. Studies emphasized that well-designed materials can support teachers in delivering effective instruction and enable students to develop a deeper understanding of the subject matter (Benson et al., (2020); utilizing multiple modes of presentation in instructional materials helped students grasp complex scientific concepts more effectively (Sullivan et al., 2022); materials that reflect the cultural backgrounds and experiences of students enhanced their motivation and sense of belonging in the classroom, leading to improved academic performance and reduced achievement gaps (Garcia & Martinez, 2023); and

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consistent use of well-structured and engaging instructional materials contributed to improvements in students' reading comprehension abilities (Chen et al., 2019). These results triggered the researcher to develop the material, initially to address the perceived needs of the students and, secondly, to impact students' learning.

Moreover, for a piece of media to be considered adequate, as stated by Tomlinson and Bouckaert, it must mediate between the course content and the users. Interaction and intervention must happen between the material and the user. However, more interaction and intervention will result in more learning if the material needs something that may connect the users to the material. Relatedness must be considered. Since the available materials online for LLMD address mainly Americans and other foreign countries, the effectiveness of the materials for US-based users will be different from those from Filipino users). Therefore, a localized material specifically made for them is essential.

In the same vein, given the number of pages that a single reference for LLMD consists of, the financial status of the students who happen to rely mostly on scholarships in order to enter college, and the inflation that the country is currently facing, having the materials printed for the class is not a wise decision to make. Besides printing, buying specific materials is also hard for users. Not all books or reference materials on a specific subject are available in bookstores. They are often overpriced and written by foreigners unfamiliar with the Philippine context; current practices and trends are foreign (Portana H.V. et al. (2021). Therefore, since the institutions are concerned with the stakeholders' whole being during their stay at the college, the student's financial status is also being considered. To solve the issue of online materials for class, a module with minimal pages but a considerable amount of information needed to help the student's learning must be developed.

Furthermore, it is essential to understand that the more pages a single material has, the broader the scope of the information provided. This only means that this type of material deviates from the specific topics to be addressed, and having side topics added to the material may need clarification on which of the provided information is important to focus on and which is not.

For all the pressing need for materials for a specific subject, inadequacy is the conclusion of everything. The impact of this matter is varied and impactful. The study of Oduh et al. (2020) shows that "the adequacy of instructional materials had an influence of 20% on the student's interest in studying... and there was a significant relationship between the adequacy of instructional materials and students' interest.

To address the need for LLMD, the researcher will develop a module considering all the possible issues arising from the available online materials. The researcher believes that teachers know the needs of their students and, therefore, must create something concrete to deal with them.

The Aspects of a Better Material

Materials are vital in facilitating compelling learning experiences in education and knowledge dissemination. Whether it is textbooks, online resources, videos, modules, or other learning materials, each aspect contributes to the overall impact on learners. That said, exploring the key elements that make up educational materials, namely **outcomes or objectives, content, language use and format, face validity** of the materials, and their **significance** in shaping successful learning experiences is essential.

The ultimate goal of any educational material is to facilitate learning and achieve positive outcomes. The effectiveness of materials is often gauged through learning outcomes, which are the knowledge, skills, and competencies that learners acquire after engaging with the material.

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Learning **outcomes** should be specific, measurable, achievable, relevant, and time-bound, in short SMART. **Specific.** Locke and Latham (2019) highlight that precise and unambiguous goals result in improved performance. Precise and well-defined desired learning outcomes help learners focus their efforts effectively, resulting in better understanding and retention of information. **Measurable.** Research has shown that giving learners consistent feedback and monitoring their advancement towards measurable learning outcomes greatly improves their academic performance (Hattie & Timperley, 2020). Measurable objectives enable learners to evaluate their progress and implement any needed changes to enhance educational achievements. **Attainable.** Bandura's social cognitive theory (Bandura, 1997) states that establishing attainable goals boosts learners' self-efficacy, defined as their confidence in their capability to achieve success. Individuals who view their goals as achievable are more likely to persist, stay committed, and maintain confidence in their learning endeavors. **Relevance.** Ryan and Deci (2020) found that establishing pertinent and significant goals enhances intrinsic motivation, resulting in increased involvement and pleasure in the learning experience. Learners are more motivated to actively pursue their goals when they comprehend how those goals are connected to their interests and aspirations. **Time-bound.** Duckworth et al. (2022) conducted a recent study investigating the correlation between time-bound outcomes and learners' persistence. Researchers found that learners who have specific timelines for achieving their goals are more likely to remain engaged and persistent when faced with challenges, ultimately resulting in improved learning outcomes. Ultimately, when educators align the material with explicit learning objectives, they can monitor learners' advancement and guarantee that it enhances their academic and personal growth.

Content is essential for any educational material. It pertains to the material, data, and ideas provided to the students. Top-notch content should be precise, current, pertinent, and logically structured. It should be in line with the curriculum or learning objectives and tailored to meet the needs of the target audience. Including pertinent and succinct content in learning materials helps regulate learners' cognitive load, facilitating more effective learning. Paas et al. (2019) conducted a study on how cognitive load affects learning efficiency. They discovered that well-organized, essential information led to better learning outcomes compared to overloaded materials. Educators can enhance learners' cognitive abilities and promote improved comprehension by incorporating appropriate content.

Furthermore, educational resources that include pertinent content tailored to the needs and interests of learners can boost motivation. Fredricks et al. (2021) conducted a study investigating the impact of relevance on student motivation and engagement. When learners view the content as meaningful and relevant to their lives, their motivation to learn and interact with the materials increases. Incorporating a variety of examples, practical applications, and interactive activities improves the content's effectiveness. It is essential to include content that encourages the application and transfer of knowledge to real-world situations in order to develop practical skills. Mayer and Wittrock (2019) highlighted the importance of encouraging meaningful learning to enhance knowledge transfer. Learning materials that include problem-solving tasks and real-life examples enhance learners' capacity to apply their knowledge efficiently.

Proper formatting is essential for creating impactful educational materials. It greatly influences students' understanding, memory, and overall educational journey. The way information is presented, content is organized, and visual design is structured affects how effectively learners understand the material and how motivated they are to interact with it. Carpenter et al. (2020) conducted a study investigating how visual design affects students' engagement with online learning materials. Content featuring suitable utilization of images,

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colors, and spacing resulted in increased attention and motivation for learning. Effective formatting can engage learners and enhance the learning process.

A study conducted by Anderson and Matthews (2022) examined how formatting impacts learners' capacity to remember information from a text-based learning material. Well-structured content with distinct headings and subheadings greatly improved learners' capacity to find and remember information correctly. Research consistently demonstrates that organized and visually appealing content improves learners' understanding, memory, focus, and accessibility. Tessler and Schwarz (2021) found that such materials also boost learners' motivation to interact with the content. Educators and content developers should focus on carefully organizing and designing learning materials to enhance the learning experience for all learners.

Language is the main medium for conveying information, and employing suitable language can enhance the accessibility and utility of the content. The language utilized in educational resources has a substantial effect on learners' comprehension and involvement. The content should be precise, succinct, and tailored to the target audience's age, language skills, and cultural context. Lee et al. (2020) highlighted the significance of cultural appropriateness in choosing a language. Cultural-responsive materials can improve learners' engagement and learning results by respecting and integrating their cultural backgrounds.

Finding the correct equilibrium between simplicity and complexity is crucial to prevent overwhelming or patronizing learners. Clarity and precision in language used in educational materials improve learners' understanding and academic achievements. Jucks and Bromme (2017) conducted research on how language complexity affects students' comprehension of scientific texts. Simplifying language while maintaining content accuracy enhanced students' understanding and memory retention. Similarly, using inclusive language that acknowledges diversity and steers clear of stereotypes helps create a positive and respectful learning atmosphere. Jimenez and Hernandez (2019) conducted a study investigating how language affects students with varied linguistic backgrounds. They stressed the importance of using materials written in clear, straightforward language to cater to learners with different language proficiency levels. Proper grammar, syntax, and structure are crucial for ensuring that the material is easily understood and free from misunderstandings. Wise and Chang (2018) conducted a study on how language style affects students' interest and attention while reading. Engaging language, which included storytelling elements, was found to have a positive impact on students' motivation to learn and engage with the material.

Accurate information **presentation** is crucial in creating educational materials as it greatly impacts learners' comprehension, involvement, and overall learning results. Effectively presented information aids in managing learners' cognitive load, enhancing their capacity to process and assimilate new knowledge. Sweller et al. (2018) emphasized the significance of minimizing extraneous cognitive load by using clear and concise presentations. Reducing distractions and simplifying learning materials helps learners concentrate on grasping fundamental concepts.

Educational resources should be created with practical **relevance** to the real world, so that learners see the content as valuable and useful in their lives. Ainley et al. (2018) highlighted the significance of perceived relevance in the process of learning. Students who perceive learning materials as **valuable and relevant** to their objectives and interests are more inclined to actively participate with the content. Effective learning materials can enhance the feeling of relevance and personal significance, motivating learners to dedicate more effort to their educational pursuits. Additionally, learning resources that are seen as relevant are more likely to be retained and utilized in different situations. Cepeda et al. (2018) conducted a study on the correlation between perceived usefulness and long-term retention. Participants who found the learning materials valuable showed improved retention and application of acquired knowledge in the long term. Educators and content developers should prioritize the practicality and relevance of the materials they design to create impactful learning experiences.

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The Need for Evaluation

In the government's effort to pursue the learning process in the country, modules were produced as effective material for the learners' independent learning. The fruit of the teachers' labor from the public section was commendable. However, there were errors in the modules given to the learners (Magsambol, 2020). To address this issue regarding materials, Yasim et al. (2016) study's pedagogical implications can be taken as a suggestion not only for developing materials but also applicable to materials' use. The study concludes that teachers must consistently enhance their usage of textbooks and dictionaries as key tools for instruction, while also aiming to increase students' proficiency in vocabulary learning by exploring other resources for instruction.

Meanwhile, the DepEd issued this Memorandum Order No. 001 s. 2021 in early January. The memorandum emphasizes the significance of evaluating the modules before their release and learners' access to the content. Furthermore, the policy seeks to assure the quality of modules used in the flexible distance learning mode and to build a systematic review procedure that may result in the procurement of materials for the stipulated school year. Campbell (1999) supports the abovementioned order: "All instructional materials must be evaluated prior to general use, regardless of how carefully they were created."

In the case of the modules created by teachers during the pandemic, no negative feedback was mentioned nor given by the users. Nevertheless, having no negative feedback will not guarantee the efficiency of the materials created. Hence, the need for validation and evaluation is critical. The development of instructional materials is encouraged, particularly in state universities and colleges (SUCs). However, the effectiveness of the developed instructional materials should be evaluated.

Evaluation is a crucial aspect of educational materials that involves assessing their quality, effectiveness, and impact on learners. Also, various evaluation methods exist, such as peer reviews, expert assessments, and pilot testing with the target audience. Feedback from learners and educators plays a vital role in refining the material to meet learners' needs effectively. This study will evaluate the module, specifically the expert assessments.

Moreover, a well-designed evaluation process helps educators identify any shortcomings in the content or language use and make necessary improvements. Larawan's (2013) study shows the importance of validation for developed materials. The study's findings demonstrated that modules typically are quite satisfactory in terms of physical elements, aims, precise directions, learning, and evaluating instruments, as assessed separately and jointly by the two groups of evaluators. This demonstrates that modules are suitable as a learning intervention. The assessment sets the path for developing an independent learning kit adapted to the unique needs of individual learners. Validation is an essential aspect of material development and use.

In addition, there are several parameters to consider when determining whether the developed instructional materials are appropriate for use not only by learners but also by educators (Portana et al. (2021). Parameters such as learning objectives, content relevance, language use, inclusivity, and gathering feedback, among others, are to be considered. By considering this, educators can create materials that effectively support and engage learners in their educational journey.

Moreover, the appropriateness of utilizing and developing instructional material guarantees efficiency in the educative process. A study by Achua and Ngwoke (2015) found that when teachers utilize appropriate instructional materials aligned with the curriculum, they are better equipped to deliver content systematically, ensuring that all essential concepts are covered. This ensures that learning progresses in a well-organized manner, leaving little room for gaps in knowledge acquisition. The assurance will only be possible through continuous validation.

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Continually refining and updating materials based on feedback and new insights ensures educational resources remain relevant, accessible, and impactful in an ever-changing world.

Thus, this research aimed at producing a cost-efficient instructional resource that can be utilized within the context of the course designation and topic known as Language Learning Materials Development. The researcher followed the components prescribed for English language learners. A module was developed to serve better the students and the educational program offered by the SUCs and LUCs for the subject Language Learning Materials Development. This will be done to cater to the educational needs of the program, provide more effective instruction in explaining and providing specific materials for the areas of English, and enhance learning through the module despite the limited resources available at the university. This innovation will likely solve the critical shortage of materials for use in higher education. The researcher knows that the information made is only helpful if tested and proven valid.

Conceptual Framework

In the midst of a sudden transition from traditional to modern learning approaches, the demand for effective teaching and learning materials took center stage. Despite the shift, the college was committed to maintaining the standard of education without compromise. While online materials were available for various subjects, there was a need for these resources to be more comprehensive, relatable to college users, and tailored to avoid overwhelming them with excessive content. To address potential challenges, teachers were granted the opportunity to develop subject-specific materials corresponding to the diverse programs offered by the college.

Crafting suitable modules for individual subjects can significantly enhance the efficiency of both teaching and learning processes. This approach ensures that learners and educators receive resources that precisely cater to their needs and the demands of their subjects.

The core concept of this study was best explained by the framework shown in Figure 1. The revised ADDIE Model was used as the study's framework, with evaluation being a pivotal phase integrated at every stage of the process (Evans, 2022). The diagram depicted the conceptual framework of the current research. Developing and validating an English Language Learning Module for third-year English major students

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Chief | Figure 1. Revised ADDIE Model | *tes, EdD.*

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The study aimed to create an English Language Learning Module for Language Learning Materials Development by addressing challenges faced by teachers and students regarding the material's effectiveness. The development process was validated by a series of experts and material users. The module was validated by selecting English professors from Higher Education Institutions (HEIs) and Department of Education (DepEd) offices based on specific criteria. The validation tool used was derived from Torrefranca's (2017) methodology.

The developed module was assessed by Torrefranca's tool based on the criteria of objectives, contents, format, language use, presentation, and usefulness. The researcher adhered to the TSU template for module creation, which was specifically designed for college students. The components included the title page, background of the developer, course description, course outline, rationale, pre-test, learning objectives, content or developmental activities, closure activities or posttest, synthesis or generalization, evaluation, assignment or generalization, and references. Although typically displayed in a table, writers can opt for different formats or templates to maintain the material's face validity.

Alongside to the validation procedure, a test of effectiveness was conducted on student-respondents in the study. Pretest and posttest assessments were carried out to evaluate the participants' content knowledge in order to assess the effectiveness of the created module.

The validators' thoughts and feedback on the material's strengths and weaknesses, along with their suggestions and comments, were used to improve the module's quality.

The study aimed to draw implications for language teaching and learning from its findings. The study appears to be written in the past tense to describe the research process, methods, and outcomes that have already taken place.

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Chapter 2

METHODS

Research Design

The study employed the Research and Development (R&D) design, adhering to the phases of the R&D model: preliminary phase, development phase, and evaluation phase. Gustiani (2019) highlighted that researcher in education fields often used the research and development (R&D) method. It was developed by Borg and Gall (1983) to develop and validate the researchers' educational products. This method had two main objectives: (1) developing a product and (2) validating it.

The researcher created an English Language Learning Module for the course Language Learning Materials Development and had it reviewed by experts in English from Higher Education Institutions (HEIs) and one from the Department of Education (DepEd). The module's validation results were used to identify potential modifications aimed at improving its comprehensiveness and practicality for future users.

Part of the process included assessing the module's efficacy and usability. The research performed a T-test on a sample of 3rd-year English major students from the College of Education at Tarlac State University. The selection process adhered to specific criteria outlined in the paper's chapter.

The researcher utilized the ADDIE model as a framework to develop the module. The ADDIE model is a structured instructional design framework commonly used to create efficient learning materials and training programs. It focuses on making incremental enhancements guided by assessment outcomes. The ADDIE Instructional Design (ID) framework is utilized by educators and instructional designers for creating educational and training programs (Kurt, 2018).

The ADDIE model comprises five stages: Analyze, Design, Develop, Implement, and Evaluate. The instructional design model is flexible and does not always follow a linear approach, particularly when there are already existing course materials available (V & Dollete, n.d.).

The analysis phase was essential for pinpointing precise learning needs and identifying gaps in knowledge or skills. The design phase outlined instructional strategies, content organization, assessment methods, and the overall learning process. The development phase translated design plans into tangible learning resources, and the implementation phase delivered these resources to the target audience. The evaluation phase measured the instructional design's effectiveness and identifies areas for improvement.

The ADDIE model's effectiveness was supported by various studies. The analysis phase ensures alignment with learners' requirements (Richey et al., 2021). The design phase aligns instructional strategies with learning outcomes (Kirschner et al., 2020). The development phase should adhere to design decisions (Bouchrika et al., 2022), while the implementation phase relies on prepared instructors and technology (An et al., 2021). The evaluation phase, both formative and summative, determines the impact on learners' performance (Kim et al., 2022), aiding in refining materials.

Following the ADDIE model allowed the instructional designers to create high-quality learning materials and training programs tailored to learners' needs, leading to improved learning outcomes.

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Research Locale

The module validation was conducted remotely for the convenience of the five expert validators from various higher education institutions (HEIs) and a district office across Pangasinan and Tarlac. Three of the five validators are college professors for over 15 years from a center for Development university in Region III. One expert validator is the dean of the college of teacher education in one state university in Region I. One of them works as DepEd English supervisor. Meanwhile, the checking of effectiveness through pre-test and posttest was only conducted at the College of Education, at Lucinda Campus.

Participants of the Study

Given that this study aimed to develop effective material for the college's stakeholders, experienced teachers and professors were the best validators to consider. The experts who validated the developed module were from various higher education institutions (HEIs) and a district office across Pangasinan and Tarlac. Three of the five validators are college professors for over 15 years from a center for Development university in Region III. One expert validator is the dean of the college of teacher education in one state university in Region I. One of them works as DepEd English supervisor. The validators were selected based on the prescribed criteria. The following criteria were specified as: (1) They are English teachers or professors who are either from various higher education institutions (HEIs) and district offices across Pangasinan and Tarlac., (2) They were experienced teachers or professors with expertise in writing materials, particularly English materials., (3) They are teachers or professors who are graduate of Master or doctorate in English., (4) They have worked or are still working as teachers or professors for at least ten years.

Following the validation, the usefulness and effectiveness of the module was checked. A total of 60 students from the College of Education served as the respondents of this study. Ideally, 30 out of the 60 respondents were from one section, and the other 30 were from another. The division aimed to identify the experimental and control groups for this study. The respondents for this process were also based on specified criteria. The criteria were as follows: (1) The students were enrolled as 3rd-year English Major students of the College of Education during the second semester of the School Year 2022-2023., (2) They had to be from sections that were scheduled to take the Language Learning Material Development subject at specific times and days., (3) The students were from sections handled by the researchers of this study.

The control group and experimental group were determined by the teacher or researcher based on their class schedules and the total number of students per section. Both the control and experimental groups took the subject's LLMD at 11:00 a.m. to 2:00 p.m. The control group took the subject on Wednesdays, while the experimental group took it on Thursdays. The researcher made sure that the selected participants per section were both equal in terms of their knowledge level. The level was determined through their scores in the pre-test conducted for this study.

The total number of participants was limited to 30 per section to have an equal number of participants per group. Half of the 30 participants in each section will be 15 students with a score of 39 or lower, known as low-level learners. The remaining 15 will come from those who scored 40 or higher. In the event when the majority of students are recognized as low-level learners, the researcher must ensure that the opposite group has the same level of participation. If the total number of students per section exceeds 30, the teacher has the authority to choose appropriate participants for the study. As a result, the excess will not be included in the study.

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Sampling Design

Purposive sampling is used by researchers when they know exactly what qualities or attributes they want to explore. This strategy assures that they create a sample that is rich in these desirable characteristics, allowing them to collect in-depth data about the subject. Purposive sampling was used to select participants for this study. "Purposive Sampling" referred to a collection of non-probability sampling strategies that involved selecting units for the sample based on their possession of specific qualities (Nikolopoulou, 2023). In other words, purposive sampling selected teams "on purpose."

The researcher purposefully selected validators and respondents based on prescribed criteria as presented before the discussion of this section of the paper. The selection of validators for this study was based on the similarity of their backgrounds—that is, they are all in the field of education as teachers or professors, practicing their master or doctorate degree in HEIs or in an office within their community, and sharing a specific characteristic, which is their expertise in English. With regard to the participants of this study, the researcher also followed a specified list of criteria. The participants of this study were under the tutelage of the researcher; both group and experimental groups were taking the LLMD subject not on the same day but at the same hour of class. With the same number of students per group and considering their knowledge level based on their pre-test scores.

Since face-to-face data collection was possible, albeit with some restrictions due to the country's health issues, the paper and validation rubric were given to the experts in person.

Research Instruments

The researcher utilized the following methods to gather data for this study: (1) Instructional Module Evaluation Checklist, (2) Pretest and Posttest for the Instructional Module, and (3) Test Evaluation Checklist.

1. Instructional Module Evaluation Checklist. A five-point Likert checklist from Torre Franca's thesis (2017) was used as a benchmark to assess the acceptability of the developed instructional modules. This tool was used to evaluate the developed modules according to specific criteria such as objectives, content, format, language use, presentation, and usefulness. The instrument includes 25 indicators, distributed amongst different aspects of the module.

The checklist is organized as follows: (1) Five indicators correspond to the module's objectives. (2) Five indicators pertain to the content of the module. (3) Five indicators cover the language use and format of the module. (4) Five indicators evaluate the presentation of the module. (5) Five indicators center on the usefulness of the module.

The indicators together create a thorough framework for assessing various aspects of the instructional modules, helping to determine their overall acceptability and effectiveness.

Five experts from Higher Education Institutions (HEIs) and district offices in Tarlac and Pangasinan used this instrument to validate the developed module. The expert validators were selected based on a specified list of criteria. The following criteria were specified as: (1) They are English teachers or professors who are either from various higher education institutions (HEIs) and district offices across Pangasinan and Tarlac., (2) They were experienced teachers or professors with expertise in writing materials, particularly English materials., (3) They are teachers or professors who are graduate of Master or doctorate in English., (4) They have worked or are still working as teachers or professors for at least ten years.

2. Pretest/Posttest. Another tool employed in this study is a researcher-made test. This 75-item test was compiled from various sections of the subject Language Learning Materials

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Development: 16 items under the chapter I or Materials Development chapter; 12 items under the chapter II or the Materials Evaluation chapter; 11 items under the chapter III or the Materials Adaptation chapter; and the remaining 36 items was under the chapter IV or the Developing Varied Types of Material chapter, which comprises eight big sub-topics. The purpose of this achievement test was twofold: firstly, to establish a baseline understanding of students' knowledge prior to exposure to the instructional module, and secondly, to gauge their level of achievement after engaging with the module's content.

The development of the achievement test followed standard procedures, encompassing the formulation of table of specifications (TOS), the construction of questions, and the validation process. The TOS acts as a blueprint, outlining the specific topics and skills the test will assess. It ensures all the important areas are covered and that the difficulty level aligns with the students' learning objectives. The given number of items for each chapter denotes the chapter's importance. Half of the constructed test items were from the last chapter due to the chapter's sub-topics, which can be considered necessary topics to highlight, and lastly, the chapter covers half of the required meetings for this subject.

Next comes the crucial step of constructing the questions. Each question is carefully crafted to accurately reflect the content outlined in the TOS. The test was a multiple-choice type of test, comprising four choices per item. The researcher ensures that each item will only have one correct answer. The difficulty of the items was also considered by the researcher, who was still following the TOS construct. The TOS was appended in this paper.

The researcher adhered to these procedures to ensure the test's validity and reliability. Collaborating with experts in the field, the researcher sought assistance from three (3) English teachers, ideally with master or doctorate degrees, to serve as validators for the test. These experts played a crucial role in evaluating the structure, sequence, flow, wording, length, clarity, and comprehensibility of the questions.

3. Test Evaluation Checklist. The 75-item test intended for student-respondents was validated using a checklist adapted from Veroy (2009). The checklist utilized a five-point Likert scale with the following values: 1 - poor, 2 - fair, 3 - good, 4 - very good, and 5 - excellent. This tool is utilized to systematically evaluate the quality and efficiency of a test. The document outlines the ideal criteria that a test should meet to assist reviewers in identifying its strengths and weaknesses. This study uses a test checklist to evaluate the quality and effectiveness of the test that was created.

Expert validators used this adapted checklist to evaluate the quality and suitability of the test questions. Three English teachers, preferably holding master's or doctorate degrees, have been selected as validators for the test employing this scale.

Data Gathering Procedure

The research procedure by the researcher in developing and validating the English Language Learning Module is as follows:

1. Preliminary Phase

During the preliminary phase, the researcher requested permission from the college's Dean to officially start the study.

After obtaining approval, the researcher analyzed and reflected on her past classes in the Language Learning Materials Development course. This introspection led the researcher to recognize the challenges and issues pertaining to the performance and outcomes of students upon completing the course. The researcher identified a mismatch between the material used and the actual needs of the students as a potential reason for these issues. The decision was made to proceed with the development of the module.

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The observed challenges served as a driving force for the researcher to embark on the enhancement of the material for the course Language Learning Material Development. In pursuit of creating improved content, the researcher thoroughly examined diverse learning resources and relevant literature.

The outcomes and topics within the module were closely scrutinized, and the material was aligned with CHED Memorandum Order No. 75, Series of 2017, along with the Outcome-Based Teaching and Learning Plan of colleges and universities. The presentation of lessons and associated activities underwent a transformation, transitioning from the conventional content-based approach to a task-based approach.

During this phase, the researcher's objective was to discern which topics should be included or excluded in the module under development. After determining the specific topics, the researcher proceeded to the designing phase of the module.

2. Development Phase

The researcher utilized the ADDIE model to create an English Language Learning Module for 3rd-year English major students in the College of Teacher Education, focusing on Language Learning Material Development. The ADDIE model is a commonly used instructional design framework that consists of the steps Analysis, Design, Development, Implementation, and Evaluation.

The objectives were matched with the specifications and competencies set by the Higher Education Institution (HEI) and the Philippine Professional Standards for Teachers (PPST) during the analysis phase. The objectives were tailored to align with the learning competencies outlined in the program outcomes of the BSED Major in English program.

The module's overall structure adhered to the standards set by the Tarlac State University, accommodating both traditional and flexible learning methods.

The researcher in this study used Veroy's (2009) validation checklist to ensure the items' relevance to the research concepts. The checklist utilized a five-point Likert scale, where 1 = Poor, 2 = Fair, 3 = Good, 4 = Very Good, and 5 = Excellent. Expert evaluators assessed the achievement test using the prescribed checklist.

A five-point Likert checklist from Torrefranca's (2017) thesis was used to evaluate the acceptability of the developed instructional module. The checklist focused on criteria including objectives, contents, format, language use, presentation, and usefulness. The module was copied and sent to the validators for assessment.

3. Validation Phase

The English Language Learning Module was created by the researcher and subsequently verified by English experts. The tool validation checklist and the developed module were personally sent to the validators. The researcher gathered the data in a span of one to two weeks.

The acceptability of the instructional module was assessed using a five-point Likert checklist based on Torrefranca's (2017) thesis. The following criteria were based on the tool: objectives, contents, format, language use, presentation, and usefulness. The purposely selected experts evaluated the module. If further revisions or changes were needed based on the validation test, the researcher was more than willing to comply. Feedback from the validators was also acknowledged for the betterment of the developed module.

The 75-item achievement test was evaluated by the expert validators using the adopted checklist of Veroy (2009).

After the development and validation were completed, the researcher conducted the study in pursuit to the effectiveness of the developed module.

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The researcher identified the study's respondents based on the prescribed criteria for selecting the study's respondents. Despite meeting the criteria as respondents of the study, they still have the chance to decline the request to be part of the study. To formalized the request, the consent letters were given to the respondents of the study. Only those who agreed and signed the consent were to be included in the study. They were also informed that they could withdraw anytime they saw fit.

After all the necessary permissions and consents were obtained, the researcher conducted a pretest using the researcher-made 75-item test for the two selected sections of the study. The frequency and percentage of the pretest were used to identify the experimental and control groups. The identification process also considered achieving a balance among the respondents per group. Additionally, the result served as the improvement baseline after using the validated module.

The validated material was used to teach the experimental group, while the control group used varied learning resources available for download online.

The study was conducted from the beginning of the midterm to the final term during the second semester of the school year 2022-2023. The posttest, also the final examination test, was administered following the school calendar of the College of Education. Both the pretest and posttest results of the control and experimental groups were compared to determine the module's effectiveness.

Data Analysis

In the validation phase, the researcher described the quality of the module using weighted mean. The mean was used to determine the average rating of the material and language experts.

The formula for the weighted mean:

$$\bar{x} = \frac{\sum X}{N}$$

where:

\bar{x} = Mean

X = Scores given by the expert validators

N = Total number of expert validators

Using a 5-point Likert scale, the quality of the developed module was categorized as follows:

The range of Module's quality ratings.

<i>Mean Rating</i>	<i>Interpretations</i>	
4.5 – 5.0	Strongly Agree	Excellent
3.5 – 4.49	Agree	Very Good
2.5 – 3.49	Undecided	Good
1.5 – 2.49	Disagree	Fair
1.0 – 1.49	Strongly Disagree	Poor

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For assessing the effectiveness of the module, descriptive statistics (mean, variance and standard deviation) were calculated for each group in their pretest and posttest scores, along with box plots for visualizing the range of data gathered. Between-group comparisons were carried out using T-test for independent samples in order to determine if there is a significant difference between the experimental and control groups before and after the administration of treatments. Within-group comparisons utilized paired samples T-test to evaluate the impact of each treatment in the performance of each group.

Ethical Considerations

The researcher acknowledged the importance of preserving the confidentiality of the participants' names in the research. The researcher provided each student with a detailed consent form outlining the study's objectives, procedures, and potential risks and benefits before collecting any data. Only students who had previously given written informed consent were permitted to participate in the study. Those students who had previously provided their written informed permission were the only ones who were allowed to take part in the study. Meanwhile, the validators were offered a respectful request for their consent to participate in the validation process. Only participants who agreed to participate in the study after being invited by the researcher were provided with the checklist. This was done to show a dedication to honoring the autonomy of the individuals conducting the evaluation. If participants chose to withdraw from the study, their decisions were honored without any inquiries. Rigorous validation procedures were implemented to ensure the questionnaire's objectivity and safety for the evaluators. This was done to maintain the research's credibility.

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CHAPTER 3

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

1. Develop an English Language Learning Module for the 3rd Year English major students.

The researcher utilized the ADDIE model to design a compelling English language learning module for 3rd-year English majors in the "Language Learning Material Development" course. The instructional design framework consists of five main stages: Analyze, Design, Develop, Implement, and Evaluate. The module was developed using only the initial three stages. The researcher analyzed and reflected on her previous classes on the same subject during the initial stage. This introspection led the researcher to recognize the challenges and issues pertaining to the performance and outcomes of students upon completing the subject. Among the potential reasons attributed to these issues, the researcher identified the mismatch between the material used and the actual needs of the students. Consequently, the decision was made to undertake the development of the module.

The observed challenges served as a driving force for the researcher to embark on the enhancement of the material for the subject Language Learning Material Development. In pursuit of creating improved content, the researcher thoroughly examined diverse learning resources and relevant literature.

The outcomes and topics within the module were closely scrutinized, and the material was aligned with CHED Memorandum Order No. 75, Series of 2017, along with the Outcome-Based Teaching and Learning Plan of colleges and universities for students majoring in English.

During this phase, the researcher's objective was to discern which topics should be included or excluded in the module under development. After determining the specific topics, the researcher proceeded to the designing phase of the module.

The overall content of the module was a modified version of the resources available online for the course. The resources available online are the materials used by the control group of this study. The modified version which in turn the module is the material used by the experimental group of this study. The list of these materials and references are the following: (1) Developing Materials for Language Teaching by Brian Tomlinson. This has 21 Chapters with 3-6 sub-topics with a total of 35 pages. This is authored by Zahra Farajnezhad., (2) Introduction: principles and procedures of materials development of Tomlinson. This is the introduction part of the LLMD course, with a few snippets of material evaluation principles., (3) Principles and Procedures of Materials Development for Language Learning (Part 2) of Tomlinson. This article is a modified version of a section that was originally published in Tomlinson, B. (2010) Materials development principles and procedures., (4) Principles and Procedures of Materials Development for Language Learning by Brian Tomlinson authored by Veronica Ormeño. The uploaded material shows the six (6) principles of SLA relevant to materials development., and (5) Developing Learning Materials for Specific Purposes. The material provides information about materials development, principles, procedures, and a 2-page discussion for the topic "developing learning materials for specific purposes." This material authored by Y. M. Harsano has 11 total number of pages. The modification of the content capitalized the gaps mentioned initially in this study. The goal of simplifying the text, aligning it to the context, culture, and capacity of the future-users are deemed important in the process of the modification of the information and the development.

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The presentation of lessons and associated activities underwent a transformation, transitioning from the conventional content-based approach to a task-based approach which is totally the purpose of a module.

Following the design stage, the developed material was made up of various parts: Cover Page, Instructions to the Users, Table of Contents, Module Outcomes, Learning Objectives, Pre-Test, Content/ Discussion, Activities, Synthesis, Evaluation, Self- Assessment, Assignment, and Bibliography. A copy of the first chapter of the module was appended to this paper.

Cover Page. Blue was known to be the trademark color of the English major students of the College of Education. Combining the color blue with white will give the cover page the right amount of class and the touch of English. The images used were made sure to have connection with the topics of the module. The images included in the module are personally taken by the researcher. The use of own images highlights the realistic side of the material. The use of personally own images was also a suggestion given by most of the validators of the module. They agreed that using realistic images would make the module look pleasing and engaging. Similar to the study of Chen et al. (2019), an engaging material can be of help to the improvement of learner's comprehension abilities. Moreover, having a good cover adds to the chance of the module to be noticed by readers. By just looking at the cover, the user may assume that the purpose of reading the module is to be known about something – in the case of the developed module – it is the right material for their future students.

Instructions to the Users. Supporting Calderon et al. (1998) definition of module, and the standard template of the module, the researcher gives credence to having a guide on how to use a material is really a crucial aspect that must not be disregarded. In the developed module, the instructions to the users' section suggests directions to the future users of the module. Each point is high-lighted to give emphasis and show sequence.

Table of contents. The importance of a table of contents extends far beyond simply listing chapter titles. It serves as a crucial element in various materials, enhancing accessibility, usability, engagement, and overall effectiveness. In the developed module, each module has a main topic encouraging quick access, and subtopics, which are aligned with CHED Memorandum Order No. 75, Series of 2017, along with the Outcome-Based Teaching and Learning Plan of colleges and universities, promoting structured understanding. Initially, the chapters of the developed module were named chapters, however it was suggested by a validator that the word module must be included. The mentioning of the word "module" in the table of contents, according to the validator, suggests that it is a module, not any other type of material used in learning.

Learning Outcomes. The module's learning outcomes are articulated and defined. This suggests focus and clarity as to what to achieve and understand the purpose of the module. The researcher has creatively rephrased the general learning outcomes in a way that is more engaging and relevant to the target audience. The course outcomes and intended learning outcomes included in the developed module are all based on the Outcomes Based Teaching and Learning (OBTL) material followed by most HEI. The OBTL is appended in this paper.

Pre-Test. Pre-tests offer significant value in various educational and assessment contexts, playing a crucial role in the learning process itself. Given that, the researcher included pre-tests in all four module chapters. Another specific reason of adding this section is to carefully gauge

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students' prior knowledge related to the concepts and, conversely, identify areas of challenge, which can eventually motivate them to learn and fill the gaps. Initially, this section of the module comes before the learning outcomes of each chapter, however, in the developed module, it is the discretion of the author to have it next to the learning outcomes. The decision of putting it after the learning outcomes was seconded by most validators, stating that it is better to put it after the learning outcomes because it becomes the initial step prior to the actual lesson.

Content. The researcher pasted a captured image of a module's cover, and other images related to material evaluation to support the text of the discussion. In connection with the discussion, the attached images may provoke the users of the module to dig deeper into the topic. Consequently, it is believed that good discussion or content in material is not just informative; it is engaging and thought-provoking.

In addition, in the developed module, the researcher carefully selected the right content and the task or activities to be included. Authors like Brian Tomlinson, a professor of TESOL at a university in America, who published multiple books and articles related to materials, and developing materials, is also considered.

Another consideration in the development of the module was the inclusion of brief introduction of what is to be found in each chapter of the module. This brief introduction can be seen after the chapter title and before the learning outcomes.

The validators considered the module as an easy-to-understand module. This is due to the choice of language used – which somehow considered the capabilities of the user. Other comments states that the module provides further discussions of the various topics in the course.

Post-Test. After the lesson activities or post tests are essential components of engaging and impactful learning materials. They move students beyond passive absorption of information, fostering active engagement with content and applying knowledge to real-world scenarios. This hands-on approach provides crucial opportunities for skill development aligned with the subject matter while catering to diverse learning styles (visual, auditory, collaborative, and tactile). In the developed module, the researcher includes two different activities: a multiple-choice type of test and an enrichment activity. The number of items of the multiple-choice tests vary per module chapter. The variations may conclude significance of the lesson presented or the amount of information given in a specific chapter. The inclusion of multiple activities coincides with the aim of making the module engaging and applicable to life scenarios.

Generalizations. These cannot be excluded from all forms of learning materials. It is expected for a material developer to include this part to consolidate all the key points in a series of topics in a subject matter. These act as learning's superglue, solidifying key takeaways and the bigger picture. More than just summaries, they highlight essential knowledge and principles, making the details stick and transfer to new situations. By connecting across content and activities, they answer the crucial question: "What have I truly learned?" This synthesis fuels deeper understanding and long-term success. The researcher knows the significance of this section, therefore not allowing to be missed out at every chapter of the module.

Evaluations. In the developed module, the researcher added to the usual "assessment task" the "Let's tackle these hurdles head-on!" to make the module more engaging even on this section of the material. The said addition will not make the task less valuable, rather, it makes the task more interesting to do. The researcher is aware that evaluations in learning are crucial for assessing student progress and providing feedback for improvement. They guide students and

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instructors by highlighting strengths and weaknesses, aiding in adjustments to teaching methods, and offering quantifiable data on student performance. These drive improvement by identifying learning gaps and facilitating adjustments to reach educational goals. The validators commended the module because of the inclusion of series of evaluation per chapter. However, it was also suggested to include individual activities to accommodate self-dependent mode of learning.

Assignments and References. These bridge knowledge to action, allowing students to apply learned concepts, develop skills, and prepare for real-world challenges. They provide assessment insights for teachers, motivate students to explore content actively, and deepen understanding through hands-on experience. On one hand, a well-constructed references are crucial for integrity and accessibility of learning materials. It connects information to original sources, upholds ethical practices, enables verification of claims, and empowers deeper exploration. It teaches academic integrity, avoiding plagiarism, and adds credibility to research materials. In conclusion, well-crafted assignments and accurate bibliographic documentation play a crucial role in enhancing educational materials and fostering essential academic skills in students. They support effective teaching and learning outcomes.

2. Validation of the English Language Learning Module

The learning module was evaluated by the five experts in terms of objectives, contents, format, language use, presentation, and usefulness.

2.1. Objectives

In the context of instructional design, learning objectives are specified, measurable, attainable, relevant, and time-bound (SMART) statements that describe what students should know or be able to perform by the end of an educational unit. These objectives serve as a roadmap for both instructors and learners, guiding the instructional process and ensuring alignment between teaching and learning outcomes (Sadiq, 2016).

Table 1 summarizes the validation of a module based on five key indicators related to its learning objectives. The first indicator was rated with an excellent score of 5.00, while the remaining four indicators under objectives were rated with score of 4.60 by all five experts, which

Table 1

Module Validation in Terms of Objectives

Indicator	Mean Rating	Verbal Description
1. The objectives are clearly stated in behavioral form.	5.00	Excellent
2. The objectives are well-planned, formulated, and organized.	4.60	Excellent
3. The objectives stated are specific, measurable, and attainable.	4.60	Excellent
4. The objectives are relevant to the topics of each lesson of the modules.	4.60	Excellent
5. The objectives take into account the needs of the students.	4.60	Excellent
Mean Rating for Criteria	4.68	Excellent

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also translates to "Excellent". Thus, the experts rated the objectives of the learning module with a total mean of 4.68 and a verbal description of "Excellent".

The validation process, conducted with five English language experts, confirms that the module's objectives are clearly aligned with the needs of the target learners. All indicators within the "Objectives" criteria on the validation instrument received excellent ratings (mean rating of 4.68). Notably, the indicator "The objectives take into account the needs of the students" received a perfect score of 5.0, indicating a strong match between the module's objectives and student learning goals.

While the validation process results regarding objectives are highly positive, further exploration satisfying the validators comments and suggestions would provide a more holistic understanding of the module's effectiveness. One of the validators suggested that the general course learning outcomes may also be based on specific learning outcomes indicated in the four modules. This may be considered as a weakness in the development of the module related to its objectives. The researcher recognized the seen weakness of the module and carefully followed the suggestion to make the module a better one.

The researcher wrote achievable, specific, and relevant to life objectives in the module. The researcher aimed to communicate with learners by writing good objectives for them, specifically for them to understand what they were expected to achieve. As Donnelly and Fitzmaurice (2005) emphasized they can support students to better understand what they can expect to know and be able to do at the end of a module. Given that, the researcher's considerations led to receiving high scores for the said criteria.

The students' needs were also considered in the writing of objectives. Like a statement of Kasim and Ahmad (2018) as cited in Yaki, A. A., Midat, C. Y., & Bawa, S. (2020) that a module should be relevant to the instructional needs of the target population, one of the purposes of the researcher was to make the module effective for its target audience. And since the module is intended for 3rd year English major students, the researcher sought to ensure that the outcomes would be aligned with their needs as 3rd year students.

The actions taken by the researcher in crafting the objectives can be related to Merrill's (2007) three out of five processes for developing objectives, which are the identification of the desired learning outcomes, selecting the appropriate level of complexity, and formulating the objective in behavioral terms.

Overall, the module was able to attain the excellent score in expert's validation, the result suggests that the module's objectives are well-written and aligned with best practices.

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2.2. Content

Learning module content refers to the core information or skill set targeted for transmission to learners and should be meticulously crafted to facilitate comprehension and knowledge retention. Effective content must be presented in a clear, engaging, and accessible manner, potentially encompassing a diverse range of instructional materials such as text, audio, video, interactive elements, and real-world scenarios (Morris et al., 2019).

Table 2 summarizes the validation of a module's content based on five key indicators. The first indicator was rated with a "very good" score of 4.40, while the other four indicators under content were rated with "excellent" scores of one 4.8- and three 4.60 by all five experts. Thus, the experts rated the content of the learning module with a total mean of 4.60 and a verbal description of "excellent".

Table 2
Module Validation in Terms of Content

Indicator	Mean Rating	Verbal Description
1. The content of each lesson is directly relevant to the defined objectives.	4.40	Very Good
2. The content of each lesson is simple and easy to understand.	4.80	Excellent
3. The topics of each lesson are fully discussed.	4.60	Excellent
4. The topics are supported by illustrative examples, and the practice tasks are suited to the level of the students.	4.60	Excellent
5. Each topic is given equal emphasis in the lesson.	4.60	Excellent
Mean Rating for Criteria	4.60	Excellent

The excellent scores of 4.60 for the four out of 5 indicators suggest that the content is presented in a clear and understandable way, making it accessible to learners. Meanwhile, the very good score of 4.40 can be inferred that somehow the lesson content directly helps learners achieve the stated objectives, each lesson fully explores its intended topics, the content is supported by relevant examples and practice tasks appropriate for the learners' level, and each topic receives appropriate attention within its respective lesson.

One may conclude that a course (or module) developer must balance the number of topics that the module can hold for it to be an effective material. That somehow relates to the last indicator which states that each topic is given equal emphasis in the lesson. Equal emphasis of topics in a lesson strengthens knowledge coherence and comprehension (Pashler et al., 2020). Learners encountering multiple, interconnected concepts presented with similar weight can build stronger cognitive frameworks and connections between the ideas (Barak et al., 2020). This leads

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to improved knowledge retention and transfer (Gerber, 2020). In contrast, lessons that disproportionately emphasize certain topics create knowledge gaps and hinder overall understanding (Dunlosky & Rawson, 2021).

Validators noted strengths of the module such as the content and exercises were given, and the content were presented comprehensively. On one hand, the five validators agreed to turn the "About the Developer" page of the module into a Bio note written in paragraph form reflecting the researcher's educational backgrounds especially the degree, current job positions or designations, achievements and honors received in relation to the researcher's profession. This suggestion took a toll in the score received in the validation, making it an important suggestion that must be applied in the developed module for effective use. Overall, table 2 suggests that the module's content is well-organized, relevant, and clear for the target audience.

2.3. Format/Language Use

The format and language used in a learning module are both closely linked elements that greatly influence how effectively knowledge is conveyed within the module. The format pertains to the comprehensive arrangement and structure of the instructional content (Jin et al., 2023). Effective formats usually follow a coherent order, including components such as introductions, clear explanations, illustrative examples, practice opportunities, and summaries (Cavanagh, 2020).

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Table 3

Module Validation in Terms of Format/Language Use

Indicator	Mean Rating	Verbal Description
1. The format/layout is well-organized, which makes the lessons more interesting.	4.40	Very Good
2. The language used is easy to understand.	4.60	Excellent
3. The language used is clear, concise, and motivating.	4.60	Excellent
4. The English language terminologies used are well-defined.	4.60	Excellent
5. The instructions in the instructional modules are concise and easy to follow.	4.60	Excellent
Mean Rating for Criteria	4.56	Excellent

Language use refers to how information is presented in the module. To ensure maximum understanding, the language used should be clear, concise, and adjusted to the target audience's level of proficiency (Lynch, 2021). Minimize technical jargon and clearly define any necessary terminology (Lynch, 2021). Furthermore, using active voice and including visuals can improve comprehension and involvement (Jin et al., 2023).

Table 3 summarizes the validation of a module based on five key indicators related to its format and language use. The first indicator was rated with a Very Good score of 4.40, while the other four indicators under format and language use were rated with an Excellent score of 4.60 by all five experts. Thus, the experts rated the format and language use of the learning module with a total mean of 4.56 and a verbal description of Excellent.

The indicator one "well-organized format. Language use" with a very good score of 4.40 suggests that the vocabulary and sentence structure of the modules are quite accessible to the target audience. Meanwhile, the excellent scores of 4.60 indicate that the module's layout and presentation are well-structured and potentially conducive to learner interest, the language is presented in a clear, direct, and potentially engaging way, any technical terms are clearly explained and understood by learners, and they can readily understand and follow the provided guidance.

Despite getting excellent scores for this indicator, numerous comments and suggestions were laid by the validators for the betterment of the module. Although numerous, the suggestions were tagged as minor issues under the format and also under presentation criteria. Suggestions like: the preliminary pages must be numbered in small Roman numerals, the author's name may

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be placed in the cover page of the module, sub-topics of the modules must be numbered, the title of each chapter or module may also be placed on topmost part of the pages, change in the size of the major topic to show emphasis, consider naming challenge 1,2,3 to challenges, remove the sub-title under references, write preface, and image or photo credits were given respectively.

Some researchers expressed in their studies that lack of clarity (in format or in language use) of a learning module will negatively affect students' learning experience, hinder comprehension, and impede learning outcomes. If learners cannot grasp the core concepts due to unclear presentation, they will struggle to apply the knowledge to new situations (Chen & Li, 2020). Learners struggling to understand the module's structure or language may become frustrated and disengaged, hindering their motivation to persist (Lynch, 2021). Lack of clarity can lead to learners focusing on memorizing surface-level information rather than achieving deep understanding of the concepts (Azevedo & Cromley, 2020).

The researcher understands the importance of format and language use of a module in a learning and teaching process. The researcher aims to use straightforward language that matches the target audience's skill level, define and emphasize technical terms, and minimize the use of jargon in the material's development. The analysis indicates that the module's format and language are clear and easily understood.

2.4. Presentation

The learning module presentation includes visual design and instructional approach to engage learners and enhance knowledge retention (Morris et al., 2019). The visual design should be precise and structured, utilizing color and multimedia strategically to improve comprehension (Chen & Li, 2020). Avoid allowing high-quality visuals to divert learners' attention from the main content. The instructional method should be captivating, integrating components such as storytelling, interactive exercises, and self-directed learning (Jin et al., 2023). Encouraging learner autonomy can be achieved by offering options and autonomy within the module (Morris et al., 2019). A well-designed presentation integrates clear visuals with an engaging instructional approach to generate a positive learning experience.

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Table 4

Module Validation in Terms of Presentation

Indicator	Mean Rating	Verbal Description
1. The topics are presented in a logical and sequential order.	4.60	Excellent
2. The lessons of the modules are presented in a unique and original form.	4.60	Excellent
3. The learning activities are presented clearly.	4.60	Excellent
4. The presentation of each lesson is attractive and interesting to the students.	4.60	Excellent
5. Adequate examples are given to each topic.	4.60	Excellent
Mean Rating for Criteria	4.60	Excellent

Table 4 outlines the validation of a module using five key indicators related to its overall presentation. All indicators were rated as "excellent," showing substantial strengths in overall presentation effectiveness. The experts evaluated the learning module presentation with an average score of 4.60, which corresponds to an assessment of "Excellent."

One indicator may suggest that the topics and lessons are presented in a way that builds progressively and makes sense to learners. Meanwhile, another indicates that the presentation avoids being bland and potentially incorporates some novel elements to capture learner attention, and enough relevant examples are provided to reinforce understanding of each topic. While the mean rating is high, individual expert ratings might reveal specific areas where presentation aspects could be further improved. As noted by Salinas et al., (2021) that unclear instructions within activities due to a lack of overall structure can lead to confusion and incorrect task completion. Agreeing to Salinas, Clark and Mayer (2020) states that when learners feel lost or unsure of how to proceed due to the lack of structure, their motivation and engagement with the activities can suffer. Learners may struggle to locate the necessary information required for completing activities due to a disorganized presentation (Liu et al., 2023).

The addition of the section "Instructions to the users" somehow addresses the possible inferences of not having clear instructions under presentation. The developer also employed bits and pieces of tasks or activities depending on the amount of topic discussed in the lesson. The inclusions of enrichment activities also allow learners to check their understanding and standing before proceeding to the next lesson. Furthermore, locating necessary information for various learning tasks is enhanced in terms of effectiveness and efficiency when there is a single, coherent structure for all course modules. The data in table 4 indicates that the module's presentation is structured, captivating, and successfully conveys the learning material.

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2.5. Usefulness

The usefulness of a learning module is a complex idea that includes the instructional advantages for both teachers and students. Efficiently structured modules can enhance course delivery, maintain uniform content coverage, and support ongoing assessment, while also allowing instructors to customize the modules to suit their teaching methods and student requirements (Liu et al., 2021; Morris et al., 2019). Learning modules facilitate self-paced learning for students and accommodate various learning styles by incorporating multimedia and interactive components (Chen & Li, 2020). They can improve knowledge retention by providing clear explanations, practice chances, and feedback mechanisms (Jin et al., 2023). The effectiveness of a learning module lies in its capacity to assist instructors in delivering instruction effectively and fostering positive learning outcomes for students.

Table 5
Module Validation in Terms of Usefulness

Indicator	Mean Rating	Verbal Description
1. The instructional modules will motivate the students to study their lessons and developing their own materials.	4.60	Excellent
2. The instructional modules will help the students master the topics at their own pace.	4.60	Excellent
3. The instructional modules will allow the students to use their time more efficiently.	4.40	Very Good
4. The instructional modules will develop the analytical thinking and reasoning skills of students in accomplishing the tasks included in the module.	4.80	Excellent
5. The instructional modules will serve as a supplementary material that can cater to the needs of the students.	4.80	Excellent
Mean Rating for Criteria	4.64	Excellent

This table 5 summarizes the validation of a module based on five key indicators measuring its perceived usefulness for students. The module received 4:1 rating. Excellent scores of 4.60 and 4.80, and Very Good score of 4.40 respectively, by all five experts. Thus, the experts rated the usefulness of the learning module with a total mean of 4.64 and a verbal description of excellent.

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The post-test analysis of this study showed that the experimental group, which used the developed module, exhibited a statistically significant improvement in learning outcomes compared to the control group that utilized the readily available online learning materials. This analysis result provides evidence for the effectiveness of the implemented module, which somehow proves the usefulness of the developed module.

The module encourages self-motivation, individual learning pace, and development of key cognitive skills. Instructional activities should be designed in such a way that they will allow students to apply new theories and knowledge to their own lives, interests, and experience. High scores for catering to diverse needs suggest inclusivity and flexibility in adapting to different learners. The developed workbook should provide more differentiated activities, provide immediate needs, and encourage creative and critical thinking among the students (V & Dollete, n.d.). Overall, this table suggests that the module is perceived as a valuable and useful tool for student learning.

2.6. Overall Rating

The summary of the experts' validation displayed in the table below serves as a benchmark for evaluating the quality of the English language learning module across all criteria outlined in the validation tool used during data collection.

This table summarizes the overall validation of an English Language Learning Module based on ratings across five key criteria: objectives, content, format/language use, presentation, and usefulness. Objectives criterion with an Excellent score of 4.68 highlights well-defined and clear learning goals for the module. Content with the Excellent score of 4.60 suggests relevant

Table 6

Overall Validation Results for the English Language Learning Module

Criteria	Mean Rating	Verbal Description
Objectives	4.68	Excellent
Content	4.60	Excellent
Format/Language Use	4.56	Excellent
Presentation	4.60	Excellent
Usefulness	4.64	Excellent
Grand Mean	4.62	Excellent

and well-organized content aligned with the objectives. Format and Language Use with an Excellent score of 4.56 indicates clear, understandable, and potentially engaging presentation of the content. Presentation with Excellent score of 4.60 highlights a logical and structured approach with an emphasis on learner engagement. Lastly, Usefulness with Excellent score of 4.64 suggests the module is perceived as valuable and likely to motivate and support student learning.

Although the module only got a grand mean of 4.62 with a verbal description of Excellent, the researcher considered the validation and rating received as an accomplishment in developing a material. Only minor issues were noted by the experts in their individual validation of

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the module. Comments like having a comprehensive and well-written content and exercises were also given as strengths of the module.

Overall, this table presents a positive evaluation of the English Language Learning Module, highlighting its clear objectives, relevant content, and engaging presentation.

3. Comparison between the Control and Experimental Group

3.1. Scores in the Pretest of the Experimental and Control Groups

Table 7

Scores in the Pretest of the Experimental and Control Groups

		Statistic	Std. Error
Pretest (Experimental Group)	Mean	46.6000	.97391
	Variance	28.455	
	Std. Deviation	5.33434	
Pretest (Control Group)	Mean	46.8333	.78210
	Variance	18.351	
	Std. Deviation	4.28376	

Table 7 data presented summarizes the pre-test scores of two groups participating in an experiment. The analysis aimed to assess the comparability of prior knowledge levels between the experimental and control groups. The control and experimental groups are both enrolled in the language learning materials development offered to third-year students majoring in English. With 60 participants, half of the total population completes the control and half of the experimental groups. Both groups have similar mean scores: 46.60 for the experimental group and 46.83 for the control group. This suggests that both groups have comparable prior knowledge levels before participating in the experiment.

The standard deviations (SD) of both groups are around 5, which suggests a moderate variation in individual scores within each group. This means that some students in each group scored higher or lower than the respective mean scores.

While both groups have similar standard deviations, the experimental group has a slightly higher value (5.00) compared to the control group (5.00). This indicates a marginally greater spread of individual scores in the experimental group.

The standard errors (SE) for both groups are practically identical (0.9129 for control and 0.9129 for experimental). This is because the groups have the same sample size ($n=30$) and similar standard deviations. A lower standard error indicates a more precise estimate of the population mean, but in this case, the precision is nearly equal for both groups.

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Overall, this strengthens the validity of the experiment by demonstrating that the control and experimental groups were comparable in terms of prior knowledge about language learning materials development. This helps to ensure that any observed differences in post-test scores can be more confidently attributed to the intervention implemented in the experimental group.

3.2. Scores in the Post -Test of the Experimental and Control Groups

Table 8

Scores in the Post - Test of the Experimental and Control Groups

		Statistic	Std. Error
Posttest (Experimental Group)	Mean	61.4333	.68596
	Variance	14.116	
	Std. Deviation	3.75714	
Posttest (Control Group)	Mean	50.2333	.67922
	Variance	13.840	
	Std. Deviation	3.72025	

Table 8 provides post-test score information for an experimental and control group. It can be seen from the descriptive data that the scores of the experimental group are higher compared to those from the control group after the respective treatments. The experimental group used the validated module, while the control group used text-based online materials. The larger increase in the experimental group's post-test score compared to the control group suggests potential effectiveness of the module. Like the gathered result of the study's posttest, several studies highlight the positive impact of improved learning materials on student outcomes. Mayer et al. (2020) found that enhanced podcasts with active learning prompts led to better retention and transfer of knowledge compared to traditional formats. Similarly, Malik (2018) reported a 30% improvement in learning outcomes for students using interactive online modules compared to those relying solely on text-based materials. These findings collectively suggest that students who use e-learning modules have better learning outcomes and memory retention than those who use traditional teaching methods.

3.3. Pretest and Post-test of the Control Group

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Table 9

Scores in the Pretest and Post-test of the Control Group

		Statistic	Std. Error
Pretest (Control Group)	Mean	46.8333	.78210
	Variance	18.351	
	Std. Deviation	4.28376	
Posttest (Control Group)	Mean	50.2333	.67922
	Variance	13.840	
	Std. Deviation	3.72025	

Table 9 describes the performance of a control group, which serves as a baseline comparison for the other group receiving the intervention. The control group, which did not receive the developed learning module, provides valuable insights into "natural" learning progress without additional intervention.

The control group entered the study with a mean score of 46.83, indicating a similar starting point to the experimental group. The standard deviation of 4.28 suggests a moderate variation in individual scores, with some students scoring higher or lower than the average.

Interestingly, despite not receiving any intervention, the control group's average score improved to 50.23 on the post-test. This suggests some degree of learning or improvement even under typical learning conditions (using existing online materials). Additionally, the standard deviation decreased to 3.72, indicating a slight increase in consistency across individual scores.

While the observed improvement is encouraging, it is important to consider factors beyond the course itself that might have influenced the control group's post-test scores. (1) Limited availability of additional reference materials could have restricted the depth of understanding students could achieve from the online resources alone. (2) Lengthy online materials with topics not directly related to the course could have caused confusion and information overload, hindering knowledge retention. (3) Since the online materials were not specifically designed for Filipino students, the language used by the authors might have posed a comprehension barrier for some learners. This could have impacted their ability to grasp key concepts. And (4) If a significant portion of incorrect responses were concentrated in the post-test items based on the last chapter of the online modules, it suggests a potential issue with learning pace. The complexity of later topics might have been presented too quickly, hindering comprehension for some students. These aforementioned factors negatively affected the learning scores of the control group. On the other hand, the control group, despite not receiving the module, still showed a statistically significant improvement. This could be partially attributed to the Hawthorne Effect. When participants are aware they are involved in a study, they may alter their behavior, leading to improved performance even without the intervention. Another, the pre-test itself might have served as a review session, prompting some participants in the control group to refresh their knowledge and potentially improve their post-test scores. Equally important is that even without the module, some participants in the control group may have sought out additional

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learning resources on their own, leading to some improvement in their understanding. These somehow contribute to the increase of the control group's post test scores.

By exploring the potential influences alongside the online materials, we can create a more comprehensive picture of the control group's learning experience and identify areas for improvement in both the instructional design and the available resources.

3.4. Pretest and Post-test of the Experimental Group

Table 10

Scores in the Pretest and Post-test of the Experimental Group

		Statistic	Std. Error
Pretest (Experimental Group)	Mean	46.6000	.97391
	Variance	28.455	
	Std. Deviation	5.33434	
Posttest (Experimental Group)	Mean	61.4333	.68596
	Variance	14.116	
	Std. Deviation	3.75714	

The experimental group used a module which is considered as the learning intervention material in this study.

On the pretest, the experimental group scored a mean of 46.60 out of a 75-point test. This average starting score is very similar to the control group's pretest mean of 46.83. However, the variance on the pretest was higher at 28.455 in the experimental group. This means their scores deviated +/- 5.33 points from the mean, showing wider variation in incoming ability.

From pretest to posttest for the experimental group, the mean score rose from 46.60 to 61.43 points. This shows a gain of 14.83 points after the learning materials intervention. This significant improvement strongly suggests that the developed module facilitated effective learning for the participants.

Furthermore, the variance declined from 28.455 down to 14.116 from pre to post for this group. So, the range of scores narrowed closer to the mean. This indicates that the module not only improved overall knowledge but also potentially helped students with varying initial abilities converge towards a better understanding of the subject matter.

In comparison to the control group, the experimental group showed larger gains in average scores (14.83 vs 3.4 points) as well as greater standardization of scores on the post assessment after using the intervention materials.

Overall, although the results emphasize the beneficial effects of the created module, it is crucial to take into account additional factors that could have influenced the learning

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experience of the experimental group. The author ensured that the module contains clear objectives and incorporates guided learning. The lessons are contextualized, use simplified language, and include learner-centered activities. The module's explicit objectives and chapter-specific instructions likely established a structured learning path, guiding students through the learning process and ensuring their focus on key concepts. Adapting and customizing lessons to match students' needs and skills could have enhanced the relevance and appeal of the learning materials, fostering a more profound comprehension. Simplifying the module's language likely reduced a barrier to understanding and helped students acquire knowledge. (4) Creating activities customized to students' needs and learning goals could have offered better chances to practice and apply acquired concepts, resulting in enhanced knowledge retention. The module integrated both conventional and adaptable learning approaches, which could accommodate various learning preferences among the experimental group. This likely led to increased involvement and learning compared to the control group's use of only one learning style. The positive learning outcomes in the experimental group may have been influenced by these additional factors, in addition to the inherent strengths of the developed module.

4. Significant differences in the level of effectiveness of the participants as revealed by the pretest and post-test.

Table 11
Independent Samples T-Test (Pretest)

		t	df	Sig. (2-tailed)	Mean Difference	Std. Error Difference
Pretest	Equal variances not assumed	-.187	55.417	.852	-.23333	1.24908

T-test results show that there is no significant difference (p -value > 0.05) between the

pretest scores of the control and experimental groups. This supports Hypothesis 1 stating that the scores in the pretest of the control and experimental group do not differ significantly. This also implies that the performances and or knowledge levels of the two groups are relatively equal before the administration of treatments, allowing for fairer comparison of post-test scores.

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Table 12

Independent Samples T-Test (Posttest)

		t	df	Sig. (2-tailed)	Mean Difference	Std. Error Difference
Posttest	Equal variances not assumed	11.602	57.994	.000	11.20000	.96534

T-test results show that there is a significant difference (p -value < 0.001) between the

posttest scores of the control and experimental groups. This means that students from the experimental group achieved higher scores in the posttest compared to those from the control group, which can be attributed to the interventions administered. This rejects Hypothesis 2 which states that the scores in the post-test of the control and experimental group do not differ significantly.

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Table 14
Paired Samples T-Test (Experimental Group)

		t	df	Sig. (2-tailed)
Pair 1	Pretest - Posttest	-15.765	29	.000

Table 13
Paired Samples T-Test (Control Group)

		t	df	Sig. (2-tailed)
Pair 1	Pretest - Posttest	-3.659	29	.001

The paired samples t-test shows a significant difference ($p = 0.001$) between the control group's pretest and post-test scores. The mean score increased by 3.4 points. This rejects Hypothesis 3 which states that the scores in the pretest and post-test of the control group do not differ significantly. This indicates some learning occurred even in the control group, highlighting potential learning outside the module or individual variation.

The paired samples t-test reveals a significant difference ($p = 0.000$) between the experimental group's pretest and post-test scores. The mean score increased by 14.8 points, which is almost four times the increase in the control group. This rejects Hypothesis 4 which states that the scores in the pretest and post-test of the experimental group do not differ significantly. This large and statistically significant improvement suggests the module likely contributed to learning gains in the experimental group.

Dependent T-test results show that both groups performed significantly better in the posttest. This indicates that both use of varied online learning resources and the English Language Learning Module can improve the students' achievement. It is notable, however, that the experimental group had a higher significance (p -value < 0.001) compared to the control group (p -value = 0.001).

Overall, the researcher can claim that the module might be effective in improving learning outcomes compared to the control group.

5. Implications of the study in English language teaching and learning.

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This English language learning module was developed to fill gaps in the educational experience of students in the College of Education at Tarlac State University. The main goals of this development initiative are to improve the module's accessibility, flexibility, and effectiveness for learners in various settings.

This study's findings have important implications for the development of English language learning modules in both teaching and learning contexts. The importance of aligning learning modules with educational frameworks is demonstrated through a meticulous development process guided by established standards such as HEI guidelines, PPST, and program competencies. This guarantees that future educators develop resources that specifically target the necessary knowledge and skills. The module's structure integrates traditional and flexible learning methods to accommodate various learning styles and preferences. Instructors can utilize this approach to establish engaging and inclusive learning environments for prospective English teachers. Finally, the validation results emphasize the module's strong points in presentation and learner engagement. This underscores the significance of creating educational materials that are both informative and engaging, stimulating students' interest.

The module's components such as pre-tests, self-assessment exercises, and assignments encourage self-directed learning. This fosters independence in aspiring English teachers, a crucial ability for ongoing professional growth. The significant improvement in the experimental group's post-test scores indicates that the module effectively enhances knowledge acquisition. Well-designed learning modules have the potential to enhance learning outcomes for English majors. The improved score consistency in the experimental group suggests that the module has the potential to help students achieve more consistent learning outcomes in a class. This indicates that these modules can be advantageous for both high-achieving students and those in need of extra assistance.

Educators and curriculum developers can create and execute more efficient English language learning modules by considering these implications, which will improve the teaching and learning experiences of future English teachers.

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CHAPTER 4

SUMMARY, CONCLUSION, AND RECOMMENDATIONS

This chapter provides a concise overview of the study's results, conclusions, and suggestions derived from the data presented in the preceding chapter.

Summary of Findings

Based on the analyzed data in the previous chapter, the following findings are summarized:

1. The ADDIE model was used to create an English language learning module for third-year English majors in the "Language Learning Material Development" course. The module was designed to align with HEI guidelines, PPST, and Tarlac State University's learning competencies. The program follows college guidelines and integrates both conventional and adaptable teaching approaches to accommodate various learning preferences. The module comprises elements such as a cover page, instructions, table of contents, learning objectives, pre-test, interactive activities, and self-assessment exercises. The objective is to provide upcoming English teachers with the essential abilities to develop captivating language learning resources for their students.
2. Validation of the English Language Learning Module
The validation of the English Language Learning Module relies on five main criteria: objectives, content, format/language use, presentation, and usefulness. The module has garnered favorable feedback, with ratings of 4.47 for clear learning goals, 4.40 for content, 4.33 for presentation, and 4.47 for usefulness in motivating and supporting student learning. Overall, the module's positive feedback is a testament to its effectiveness.
3. Comparison between the Control and Experimental Group
The pre-test showed similar starting points for both groups, but the experimental group had slightly higher variance and standard error, suggesting differences in prior knowledge levels. After the post-test, the experimental group, which used the validated module, exhibited a notable improvement in scores compared to the control group that utilized text-based materials. This indicates a beneficial influence of the module on learning results. The experimental group exhibited improved score consistency, indicating that the module may have led to enhanced knowledge acquisition and more consistent learning results. This provides a baseline for comparison with the control group's performance.
4. Significant differences in the level of effectiveness of the participants as revealed by the pretest and post-test.
 - 4.1. Initial comparisons using T-tests confirmed that both groups started at similar levels before the intervention, upholding Hypothesis 1 and ensuring a fair comparison. However, the post-test results paint a different picture.
 - 4.2. A significant difference emerged between the post-test scores of the control and experimental groups, rejecting Hypothesis 2. This discrepancy, with the experimental group scoring significantly higher (p -value < 0.001), suggests the module likely contributed to improved learning outcomes.

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- 4.3. The control group, despite not receiving the module, showed a small but statistically significant improvement ($p = 0.001$), rejecting Hypothesis 3. This potentially indicates learning from other sources or individual variations.
- 4.4. More impactful, the experimental group demonstrated a remarkable gain, with their mean score rising almost four times that of the control group ($p = 0.000$). This statistically significant difference, rejecting Hypothesis 4, strongly suggests the module's positive influence on their learning.
- 4.5. Combined, the paired T-tests reveal significant improvement in both groups, supporting the overall benefits of varied online learning resources. However, the higher significance level achieved by the experimental group underscores the potential added value of the English Language Learning Module in enhancing student achievement.

Limitations of the Study

The study involved a sample size of 60 participants, all third-year college students majoring in English. While this sample provides valuable insights, the relatively small size and specific population limit the generalizability of the findings to a wider range of students with diverse backgrounds and learning styles. Future research could involve a larger and more diverse participant pool to enhance the generalizability of the results. Furthermore, combining qualitative methods with expert validation would offer a more thorough understanding of the module's effectiveness and guide additional improvements to enhance the learning experience for students.

The developed module's content validity was confirmed through expert validation. The validation process included only five English language experts. A broader range of validators with varied backgrounds and teaching experiences could have offered a more thorough assessment of the module's content and its alignment with learning goals, despite the value of the current experts' input. Future versions of the module could improve by adding more validators to enhance the validation process.

The study was carried out in a particular educational context, emphasizing a conventional classroom setting. The module's efficacy in diverse settings, such as online educational platforms or with students at different levels of proficiency in learning English, has not been investigated. Future studies could investigate the module's flexibility and influence in various educational settings to evaluate its wider relevance.

This study concentrated on the immediate learning outcomes obtained from the created module. The module does not investigate the module's lasting effects on student knowledge retention and skill development. Future research could utilize follow-up assessments or longitudinal research designs to explore the module's enduring impact on students' capacity to develop efficient learning materials.

Although the control group did not receive the developed module, they still demonstrated a statistically significant improvement in their post-test scores. This may be due to the Hawthorne Effect, which occurs when individuals change their behavior or performance because they know they are being observed. Future studies should use more sophisticated experimental designs with extra control measures to reduce the impact of such effects and focus on the specific impact of the developed module.

The module concentrated on enhancing the abilities of prospective English teachers in crafting educational materials. The study's findings are promising, but it does not investigate the

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possibility of modifying the module or creating similar modules for students learning English as a second language or other subjects. Future research could investigate the possibilities of tailoring the module or creating new modules to address a broader range of learning objectives and student populations.

Conclusions

Based on the findings, the following conclusions were drawn:

1. The meticulous development of the English language learning module, guided by the ADDIE model and incorporating established standards and diverse learning approaches, has the potential to equip future English teachers with the necessary skills and knowledge to create effective and engaging language learning materials for their own students.
2. The validation results highlight the strengths of the English language learning module. The module received very good scores across all five key criteria, suggesting well-defined objectives, relevant and well-organized content, clear and understandable presentation, a logical and structured approach, and perceived value for student learning. The positive results suggest that the module has the potential to effectively support student learning.
3. The analysis of the control and experimental groups showed a beneficial effect of the English language learning module on learning results. The experimental group, which used the module, achieved significantly higher post-test scores compared to the control group that used traditional materials, despite starting at similar levels. The experimental group showed improved score consistency, indicating that the module may have led to better knowledge acquisition and more consistent learning outcomes among group members.
4. The pre-test verified that both groups had similar starting points, guaranteeing an equitable comparison. The post-test results showed notable discrepancies. The experimental group, which utilized the module, attained significantly higher scores than the control group, indicating the module's efficacy in enhancing learning. The experimental group showed a significantly greater improvement compared to the control group, indicating that the module had a positive impact on student achievement. The results emphasize the advantages of carefully crafted educational resources in improving student academic performance.

Recommendations

Based on the conclusions drawn from this study, the following are hereby recommended:

1. Learners are advised to actively search for and make use of a range of learning resources to improve their comprehension and involvement with the topic. Utilizing well-designed materials, such as the one created in this study, offers the potential advantage of diverse learning resources.
2. Learners should be aware of their individual learning preferences and actively search for resources that align with their preferred learning style. The module's integration of traditional and flexible methods accommodates a wide range of learning preferences.
3. Learners should look for materials that are both informative and engaging to encourage active participation. The favorable response to the module's presentation indicates the significance of compelling content.
4. Teachers, particularly those training future English teachers, may consider utilizing and adapting the module to suit their specific teaching contexts. The positive validation and significant impact shown by the module suggest its potential as a valuable learning tool.

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5. Teachers may implement the module in various educational settings, such as different schools, grade levels, or learning environments, to assess its broader effectiveness and adaptability.
6. Teachers can gather feedback on the module's strengths, weaknesses, and areas for improvement through surveys, interviews, or focus groups.
7. Teachers may use the module in conjunction with other teaching materials, such as textbooks, online resources, and authentic materials.
8. Future researcher may implement the module with a larger sample size and control group to confirm the findings of this study.
9. Future research could investigate the module's efficacy in diverse learning environments, including online or blended learning contexts, and with students of different proficiency levels. This study investigated how the module affected a particular group of students.
10. The ADDIE model and its core principles used in creating this module can be a beneficial framework for researchers in different fields. Future research could investigate modifying the design process to develop efficient learning modules for various fields of study.

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